

The Expressive Space of the Edge: the *pathos* of experience

Konstantinos Ioannidis, Department of Urban Design, Aarhus School of Architecture - Denmark

Abstract:

Never before had the vital relation between coastline and human emotion played the most affective role to urban design process than nowadays where cities are determined to return these areas back to citizens and restore all these notions-meanings that have, so violently, been removed from the urban waterfront as a result of the socio-economic changes of the last decades. But in most times this effort is muddled by amateurish attempts at generalization with standardized architectural practices. They usually neglect the study of the mediate zone between water and emotion-creation and common logic pushes away its rhetoric capacity as foolish and nonsensical, as a damned anamnesis. This space, from now on submitted to the laws of unconsciousness, requires a new planning and design concept: the Expressive Space (hereafter E.S.), which encapsulates applied research from different scientific fields, such as behavioral sciences and psychology. This paper would suggest a phenomenological frame based upon the *pathos* of human experience within a spatially meaningful and multi-sensory Edge, exploiting the specifics of our culture, behavior and derived emotions along shoreline. In the following paper, our interest will be focused on an exploration of the environmental psychology of waterfront areas and emphasis will be placed on the role of water-notion as context in human function able to model emotional phenomena by practicing imagination within urban design. In light of the research, a few important conclusions have been reached as to the value and contribution of diverse emotional states and behaviors to the urban design process and spatial construction of Edge's meaningful space.

Keywords: spatial meaning, emotional experience, meaningful space

Introduction

From Piraeus to Marseille, Portsmouth to Copenhagen, London to Helsinki, ports and harbor-cities are places that exist by definition at the Edge and thereby in intimate contact with the liquid element. The nature of this connection – of the gradual or sudden transition from land to water – affects not only the way that people built around the Edge to accommodate their lives in accordance with the offered physical setting but also their behavior and every day mood. Places make us who we are and as difficult as it is to exactly define the reason why people who feel depressed and sad seek to reach the liquid element (seashore, rivershore, lakeshore) for the experience of a magic mirroring of city's idol - denuded from any true substance - in order to change for a better mood, the same ambiguity prevails on our attempt to precisely explain how water influences not only architecture and urban design but also solutions to urban distress. While experience is clearly directed to the external material world of the seaside areas, the human *pathos* for intentional esoteric reactions to the latter is more ambiguous. Paul Ricoeur in the *Fallible Man* notes about this ambiguity: Emotion is “...

without doubt intentional: it is a feeling of “something” – the lovable, the hateful [for instance]. But it is a very strange intentionality which on the one hand designates qualities felt on things, on persons, on the world, and on the other hand manifests and reveals the way in which the self is inwardly affected. In emotion an intention and affection coincide in the same experience” (Ricoeur, 1967). Just as there is an implication of qualities felt *on* things, there is an implication of architecture which arranges these things. However, in the more recent literature on waterfront redevelopments we find virtually nothing on the behavioral aspects of the coastal space, let alone their psychological or symbolic impacts inside human emotion - and without the latter, city’s Edge remains a mere byproduct of space production which reduces its constructions to sterile shelters of the meaningless. Thus, in this paper I wish to highlight an aspect of the “socially expressive waterfront” which is problematised through a “structure of feelings”-approach to our every day’s expressions and performances along the coastline. Through this problematisation I aim to indicate the disruptive position occupied by the “emotion” inside the space of the Edge and also inside our way of conceiving the latter as a *semantic topos*.

The *Pathos* of Experience: towards a dislocation of Edge’s meaningful space

The meaning of opening up here the full range of *the pathos of experience* is to show how primary human feelings are closely attached to one’s meaningful experiences and psychical bonding with the *topos* around the Edge. The question about emotions, as evoked by the built environment in a rather idiosyncratic way (since different people can have different feelings towards the same setting), can also be repeated more profoundly in the direction of the contained universal patterns which are to be identified in the underlying process of how these emotions are evoked. This question, however, does become a theme not only for architectural psychology in general but even for a thought of human’s future well-being inside dense urban textures who would seek to take a step outside the contemporary overflowing urban “ontology”. And again, although people rarely do they understand this and consciously focus on the built environment – as a result from life’s fast rhythm- the effects of living within it are mirrored upon their behavior. In some places they can hardly help feeling boredom, timidity, annoyance even disgust; in others amazement, surprise, sociable or peacefulness. This is about psychological consequences. However, as far as liquid element eliminates the stress and noise of the busy city core and summons up a plethora of such aroused feelings along with notions, emotions, signs, ideas for our mind and imagination to be fed on, city

which stands some meters away from the coastline, tends to grasp designer's intention, in order to be benefited by this poetic invasion into the whole architectural process.

Of course we do not forget that in clear psychological terms, emotional states are complex constructions and can not be easily defined. In fact, never before in the history of architecture had designers to face so many complex structures, concerning the *ethic of space*, pressures, dilemmas and indifference than today! Therefore how is it possible for urban design, a mental procedure aiming at solving urbanistic problems, to be able to generate emotions within a continuum? A tentative answer could be by activating users by means of meaningful spatial experiences, like participatory public art for example. The degree of aroused feelings in which each one of us experience space varies. It can be almost insignificant (take for example the industrial Edge occupied by factories where people couldn't find reasons to approach with their activation level [1] on shoreline near zero) or can reach an extreme level (the opportunities for interaction and experiences on the waterfront of Barcelona after the completion of the Olympic projects demonstrates therefore a high activation level).

The problem designer faces here, in his attempt to offer possibilities for aroused emotions, is twofold: the level of arousal and what kind of it. The first, *quantitative* parameter, is related to how intense the proposed activities are, how well are implicated with the *sense of topos* and the notion of water. They can also refer to periodicity: how often we meet water-based activities during our stroll on the Edge and how easily are accessible. The second *qualitative* parameter is more intangible because it has to do with effects on our souls produced by external agents. By this we mean whether or not one feels comfortable experiencing this "arrangement of incidents", energetic, stimulated, relaxed or pace. These effects must not be transient, as a result from the prevailed disassociation of meaning from the stimulus which in many cases has already created "dead", cruel spaces; but rather from a long-lasting experiential system, able to work deep inside us and affect mood and behavior.

Emotional Products

It is not easy to probe into the structure of the emotional channels of this system, since they are as complicated as the entire human *psyche* – that is to say as complex as The Being itself. Nevertheless, up to the event which I wish to mark out and define the crucial role of man's *pathos of experience* within the experience of the urban Edge, I will first attempt a displacement of its structure by identifying the feelings involved, their frequency and

intensity. They will be organized into a model of basic emotions emerging inside patterns of behavior along the Edge as these have been allocated across the study of a plethora of waterfront projects which promote them. Sound along the shoreline is not the only that can arouse human emotion to a more intense level than the view of the open sea for example alone. Smells, haptic contact with the material world, thermal conditions as well as urban aesthetics and public art are all cues of the built environment which inform, indulge, satisfy or disappoint people.

The work of Plutchik has shed enough light on the conceptualization of *primary*, as he calls them, emotions which can be found involved inside different patterns of human behavior. He structures them into four *emotional differentials*, that is, dyads of oppositional feelings. And these are joy-sorrow, anger-fear, acceptance-rejection and surprise-anticipation. Plutchik also attempts to model these emotions into a system of axis ranging from maximum arousal of emotions to minimum arousal that is passive and non specific feelings. The following diagram [Table 1] adopts Plutchik’s primary emotions and intensity scale and illustrates his codification in a representative way to make them clear to reader, since we will use them later to explain Edge’s environmental affects.

PRIMARY EMOTIONS		INTENSITY SCALE					
		5	4	3	2	1	0
JOY		ecstasy	rapture	joy	happiness	pleasure	non-specific
SORROW			grief	sorrow	dejection	pensiveness	
ANGER		fury	rage	anger	irritation	annoyance	
FEAR		terror	panic	fear	apprehension	timidity	
ACCEPTANCE				approval	acceptance	tolerance	
REJECTION			loathing	disgust	dislike	boredom	non-specific
SURPRISE			astonishment	amazement	surprise	bewilderment	
ANTICIPATION				anticipation	expectancy	attentiveness	

Table1, Emotional differentials adapted from Plutchik P., *The Emotions*

If the entire history of emotions provoked by water can be reassembled and represented within the E.S and by the architecture of the Edge, if Plutchik’s codification touches upon the difference between maximum arousal and minimum of complete passivity, then feelings can be read inside waterfront projects depending on the activity and behavior patterns designer will accommodate and the dominance of water-notion inside them. Usually artistic constructions, like participatory water-events, inside urban design proposals are been structured in such a way to arise an emotional mixing; various combinations of feelings with result more intense experiences. For example a seaside sub-area dedicated for children playground which incorporates water games can have double impacts on a child: surprise from one hand and fear from the other. So the final sense would be this of alarm state, of awe on behalf of the user-kid. In another case, like the water events at Lisbon’s new waterfront [Figure 1], addressed also to adults, have multiple effects on people’s psyche depending on the group they belong to. Teenagers while participating and combining the nostalgic view and hearings of water they may feel acceptance from the whole spatial constructions in general but also sorrow or nostalgia. Inevitably a short of resignation and sentimentality is what follows. The same events, when experienced by adults they provoke instead both joy and surprise and make them feel delight as well. Here the, what I call, “*emotional product*” results exactly from mixtures of primary emotions at about medium intensity, showing a notation of absolute knowledge (in the Aristotelian sense) of place and even the servility of water’s spatial meaning. By this I mean that this product in silence traces the structure of experience, sketches a part of the E.S., ventures to contrive “absolute intensity” with reference to the duration of the experience (the longer the duration, the bigger the mixture of primary emotions) and finally concretizes the relationship between *psyche*, experience and space. And if this relationship seems now clearer, general rules are still difficult to be formulated.

Figure 1, Citizens usually are looking for challenge and intense experience near water – but rarely find it. Teenagers exploring a participatory water event at Lisbon’s New Waterfront.

Two factors confuse the issue of this relation. One is that experiencing the spatial meaning feeds on contrast. For example, an arrangement of meaningful incidents along the Edge –and lets take for example the sixteen “*Green Rooms*” of Nikiforidis’ proposal for Thessaloniki’s waterfront [Figure 2] - are compact and well articulated situations (which transmit very specific spatial information about the place and the history of this port city) compared with the “endless” and vast liquid element standing just in front of them. From inside these “Rooms”, the meaning of sea (as a material force which influences human lives) beyond looks broad and lacking in definition, but at the same time sea is itself a well-defined entity compared with the city-plain onto which it, in turn, opens. The second factor is that culture and experience strongly influence the interpretation of the notion of the liquid element and its spatiality. Based upon these factors, architect can start to construct spatial meanings and produce the “unstated space” of the Edge offering spatial conditions that accentuate the difference in emotional temperature within a variety of users. But the meaning of these spatial conditions gains immeasurably in power and clarity when it can be directly derived from the active manipulation of the above mentioned “*primary emotions*”. By this I mean that, for example, in a case in which the construction of a meaningful sub-space near water incorporates the spatial condition of enclosure and its following consequences – undisturbed users from passersby or feelings of tolerance for the whole atmosphere- design can manipulate human relations and emotions and rise them to a great extent and reach them to, an even, uncomfortable level of warmth.

Figure 2, Behavioral circuits incorporated within spatial conditions of sunken levels in the proposal of the Green Rooms for Thessaloniki. Architects: Nikiforidis P., Atelier R. Castro.

At this point we must also let our reading be guided by the investment of a design example which manifests some aroused emotions and their manipulation since up to now, we have been interested in the “*meaning-genesis*” problem able to create emotional products outside the borders of pure symbolization and semantic dressing. It is the radicalization of the presupposition set by water’s spatial meaning on human behavioral patterns that make the transition to the symbolic attitude necessary at this point so let us now catch up with the same problem in the field of symbolization. For the experiential and exploratory water-event in the waterfront of lake Constance, Germany set up by Dreiseitl and Holste back in 1991 [Figure 3], the meaning of meaning, the meaningful unity of the words “construction of spatial relationships”, to which this research is so attentive, has been linked with pragmatic and rational conditions: the feelings of people that have been separated, the effect of the melting snow on the other side of the lake that makes water to rise, the memory of events acted elsewhere. The adopted design approach is that of a *poetic realism* which actively utilizes place’s natural geography and topology. Moreover, the designed episode offers to people ways to explore not only their feelings about the liquid element but also the projection of their spatial configuration upon a participatory experience.

It is about a landmark on the landing pier made of stone, bronze and water. A bronze figure 4.5 meters high grows up out of twelve upright stones. It faces south, and forms a sensitive point at which the forces of sun, water and wind seem to be concentrated. Its gesture is open to interpretation: water, falling and atomizing according to the strength of the wind gives it a sense of lightness, and can transform rigid metal into a waving flag. It points to the sky, stands in the water, and mediates between the two. When the lake floods parts of the fountain when the snow melts in summer people are reminded of things that are happening beyond the sculpture, in the far distance. Perhaps a boat is departing for that destination (Dreiseitl, Graw & Ludwig, 2002).

Figure 3, Psychographic Symbolization: a landmark on lake Constance, Germany.
Designers: Dreiseitl H., Holste W.

An artistic exploratory event-landmark loaded with manifold symbolizations is placed just on the shoreline, appearing and disappearing in the eyes of users depending on the water level which constantly rises and falls. The image of the structure when mostly vanished beneath the liquid mass, affects human emotional state and nostalgic emotional products may also rise at the moment. Simultaneously the space around is active and social. It allows people to express themselves and respond to the environment. Parents often bring their children there to let them interact with this sculptural complex on the Edge, touch it, climb on it, play in it while themselves can linger on its attractive and focal points interpreting the meaning of *living by water*. For this, the almost theoretical import of the *psychographic symbolization* of the moving water level projected upon this design example is clearly refined and some more emotional products will eventually be devoted to it. It is with thoughts and memories still to come, rather than with a material construction dominated by rules of a rudimentary design approach that the composition of spatial relationships in the social space around occurs at first place.

The Infallible Pattern of Art

Maybe the incorporation of “feeling and thought” within the aesthetic experiential process of living by water can eventually offer *pleasantness* to users, since the latter is derived from the fulfillment of the above two. But only a broad definition of aesthetic experience would encompass the aspect of *emotion* within this process. The built environment of the Edge is not only a nested set of behavioral settings but is also capable of communicating messages

and producing signs for emotion-creation; then it is not an exaggeration to say that the whole urban project can bear resemblance with a piece of art. If some of its sub-areas are constructed images of feelings (designer's or user's) then a successful waterfront is an entire functional realm made visible and tangible. As Langer put it: "...*the architect creates a culture's image: a physical present human environment that expresses the characteristic rhythmic functional patterns which constitute a culture...*" (Langer, 1977)

The basic hypothesis here is thus that people's emotional responses to the Edge are mostly to its structure as expressive and behavioral patterns but also as a configuration of a "work of art", incorporating if necessary artistic events. Such events persuade us to attend to the ephemeral of the area and the insignificant of its composed parts – to moments, materials, things, constructions even people that pass us by as we perform our life near water in a way that seems to have permanence and that has tremendous impacts in our perceptual fields. The result is indeed "emotional products" and designers can take advantage of their importance and necessity, incorporating them inside the development of specific spaces with aim the creation of delight, surprise, curiosity, expectancy, optimism even pride to users and enhance civic life on the Edge. This configuration (of the *pathos of experience* inside design practices) is by far the most intangible property of the E.S. because it changes through time, culture and location depending on how fast users' perception of its messages (even the associational ones) changes. To make that more clear, some of the participatory water-events on Lisbon's Parque das Nacoas may not have been regarded as important ones or as works of art at the time of their construction but they definitely are now because of the memory left behind of an important for the city ephemeral event, as the Expo exposition whose topic, *The Ocean*, was also water related.

That which eventually escapes the abstract – for architectural discourses – concept of the *pathos of experience* and links it with design practice is not the existence of "events" in general but the existence of Art inside them (and I use the term Art in the broader sense possible). And first of all because, despite all appearances, there is no concept for the "pathos of experience". It exists and takes form only through out activity patterns and other meaningful spatial compositions during our experiences along the Edge; patterns which support human creativity, imagination, urban play or participation and use the concept of water (analogically, metaphorically or literally) to create morphologies that can be used, consumed, manipulated, sat on, viewed, walked under, changed, dismantled... We find

similar patterns organized along Lisbon's Parque das Nacoas or inside the sixteen "Green Rooms" for Thessaloniki or in Barcelona's Nova Icaria and we pointed out that they can intrigue participants, promote contact and communication of signs, messages or behaviors.

The opportunity for social interaction which neutralizes anonymity and passivity is not autonomously Art's consequence. Art becomes just the medium to provide comfort and amenity to people by incorporating elements that are subjects of study within the E.S., such as raised or sunken plazas, platforms and ledges for seating or leaning, enclosed sub-areas and more others. It also makes use of other stimuli-origimators such as sounds, sensory materials, plants or even notions like mythologies, metaphors and historical evidences. The amenities it governs can be legitimately and fruitfully applied to users and transform them into active participants or cryptographers of semantic meanings. The *Wave Garden* and the *Water Garden* in Lisbon [Figure 4] were designed by Risco (Joao de Almeida and Fernanda Fragateiro) with people's participation as a major design criterion to transfer meanings. Placed on a perpendicular axis to the Ocean Boulevard, connect it with the river and evoke the idea of water as a basic element of the landscape, given that these gardens begin with a curved wall which contains a tank from which pours a stream of water which, in the first instance, crosses a grove of palm trees, flows into a lake framed by a building and ends up winding along, once again as a stream, down by the river Tagus. In the direction of Olivais Dock, two green rectangles are explicitly shaped like waves. The work of the artist Fernanda Fragateiro is spread throughout the Water Gardens: mosaics or ceramic tiles, the lawn of the rectangle next to the Tagus which is shaped like waves and a giraffe which is admiring itself in the mirror (Toussaint, 1998). Groups from every age range and sex enjoy participation in these gardens-events; interact with water, physically since it stands in front of their feet but also mentally and semantically since the view of the open ocean creates multiple feelings.

Figure 4, Greater amount of social interaction is related with spaces that “*talk to people*” - that is with spaces where the existence of an ultimate rhetoric and poetic elements, like the liquid one, affects participants’ emotional states. *Water Gardens* in the Parque das Nacoas, Lisbon.

The latter is facilitated by Fernanda’s approach which is more focused on the semantic meaning of environmental elements (water, sand, rocks, pebbles, water-plants) and not only on the patterns of the contained structures *per se*. The used materials are clearly linked with the sense of space and the social life which is enacted around them. Edge’s spatial meaning in this case is thus a learned association between the objects and the underlying concept artist used; and this because it results from the combination of particular actions or experiences with particular meanings. As far as I am authorized to express purely personal deductions after my own interaction with the space, I would rather say that this experience is not about “ordinary social places” that usually are been called “water-parks” in mundane every day’s circumstances. It is about artistic objects put into some subareas of the waterfront which in their turn these objects form *other* spaces and give each of these more or less loose or rigid meanings which users, including me, take to be “*social*”. This may perhaps was recognized

by the space-divisions inside them which subsequently were making divisions to people and to the way human body eventually was finding the way of its occupancy (level differences, steps, edges, plant divisions, water divisions). And even now, after the end of the major ephemeral event Expo 98', these expressions of *semantic topos* keep holding people together and social relations near the coastline while allowing them to extend across time.

In fact the E.S. does not *simply* use constructed metaphor or semantic water signs, being without spatial configuration, to embody them into a dominant structure; it doesn't raise them into a method of manipulating the space of the Edge for solely rhetoric purposes. If such metaphors are indispensable it is perhaps because they illuminate the spatial meaning subtly – but clearly- as a trace around of which a lively space for people will be structured. For this reason when designers attempt to allocate artistic events within the urban space near water, these must neither be placed in a clear symmetrical logic nor consisting geometrical centers of sub-areas. And this because such an approach suggest that the place is solely designed to accommodate the events (or even worst the curiosity of the artist) and not for people. Thus off-center locations are preferable, close to facilities which attract more users. To better conceive this, we have to return back to the artistic *Parque das Nacoas* in Lisbon [Figure 5] and observe this very issue. Water gardens are of course the central concept for the organization of the area (by means of urban furniture and public art) but without outweighing the desire to make people feel comfortable and actively use the place. Useful design guidelines can be derived from the whole *choreography* of elements that incorporate, from one hand, the idea of water and are structured, on the other, in non-predictable points, destroying the homogeneity derived from standardized design practices and simultaneously offering the possibility to participants to enjoy the use of restaurants, kiosks and stalls which are been located within the very structure of the chosen choreography. And it is because of this “inaugural” choreography that interest is not focused upon a singular sculpture or a floating platform or a water fountain but instead in the whole design of the Edge: the whole area is considered an artistic pattern which also embodies behavioral and emotional circuits and for this reason can manipulate human actions, like user's motion, state of occupancy, observation and *stasis*.

Figure 5, The participant does not know where this arrangement it is going; no knowledge can render it in the exact same way in different times but the process emphasizes the impacts of its individual parts in order to create benefits above and beyond issues, such as artist's personal statements. *Choreography of Art and Water* in the Parque das Nacoas, Lisbon.

Epilogue

Therefore, there is no insurance against the meaningful space of the Edge within urban design projects since it is rather the meaning of our derived experiences that form this space and not the ontological nature of the contained objects. It is all about emotions and not at all about rational thinking. Emotions, so subtle and elusive, are being derived from a variety of sources and thus can not obey traditional and technical rules. Rules, guidelines and design recommendations are only valid for the reactive level; but when the notion of “water as context” intervenes, much more delicate sensitivities are being interwoven to our experiences with space. As notion of water affects the soul directly, behavioral patterns are much better guides than every contemporary urbanistic theory for spatial development. It was for this reason that we adopted this rather psychosemiotic stance offering a broader point of view,

with as much borders less as possible, considering spatial meaning an emotion-making force which conveys messages, signs and values. And at the same time could also be a conduit by itself. And it is here to understand the E.S. as the social and cultural force of urban design in terms of messages transmission on the Edge. The force by which this system penetrates inside our souls and ways of expressing ourselves bears resemblance with the action of Foucault's "micro-technologies of power". And this because the derived effects on our emotions from experiencing similar projects are like "*the circulation of effects of power through progressively finer channels, gaining access to individuals themselves, to their bodies, their gestures and all their daily actions*" (Foucault, 1980).

NOTES

[1] *Activation level* is a psychological notion explored extensively by Berlyne (1960) describing arousal and activation within a continuum.

REFERENCES

Berlyne, D. 1960. *Conflict, arousal and curiosity*. New York: McGraw-Hill.

Dreiseitl, H., Graw, D. and Ludwig, K. (2002) *Waterscapes: planning, building and designing with water*. Basel: Birkhauser.

Foucault, M. 1980. *Power/Knowledge: selected interviews and other writings 1972-1977*, edited by Gordon C., New York: Pantheon, 151-152.

Langer, S. 1977. *Feeling and Form: a theory of art developed from Philosophy in a New Key*, Prentice Hall, 96.

Nikiforidis P. and Castro, R. 2001. *Competition booklet for the redesign of Thessaloniki's Waterfront*. Thessaloniki: Municipality of Thessaloniki, City planning department.

Plutchik, R. 1962. *The Emotions*. New York: Random House.

Ricoeur, P. 1967. *Fallible Man: philosophy of the will*. Chicago: Henry Regnery Co., 127.

Toussaint, M. 1998. "The Expo 98' Site." In *Lisbon EXPO '98*, edited by Trigueiros, L., Sat, C. and Oliveira, C., 55-66. Editorial Blau.

Konstantinos Ioannidis, Ph.D cand., born in Greece, is currently finishing his Doctoral Studies at the Aarhus school of Architecture, Denmark and works as an assistant at the department of Landscape and Urban Design (from 2001). He is an architect graduate of Aristotle University of Thessaloniki and Member of the Technical Chamber of Greece. He gained academic experience by visiting universities in Poland (Silesian Technical University of Gliwice) and Finland (Tampere University of Technology, Helsinki University of Technology). He worked in Greece at Aristotle University, department of Urban Planning (1999) and as a research fellow (2001) in the department of Architectural Design in a program part of the projects for the Olympic Games “*Athens 2004*”. He participated in many conferences along Europe, Canada and Japan and worked as guest assistant for the procedures of a summer school. The main area of his interest and research is the architecture of the urban waterfronts and the human-centered organization of these areas.